

A theoretical model for ufra control. The yield response to late sowing or transplanting in a field affected by ufra is a trade-off between two potential yield functions. Bangladesh.

changed to achieve this effect (e.g. by shifting to a variety that flowers earlier or by the use of pregerminated seed instead of dry seeding), the maximum yields associated with the two functions may not coincide. The base yield of the function Y'' , if the crop is sown at the usual time, may not be zero.

The boundary of the shaded area in the figure defines the yield response that may be achieved by use of the practice. If the functions Y' and Y'' overlap, there will be an interior solution for the optimum time of sowing or transplanting (t^*), which gives the maximum attainable yield (y^*). The precise location of the functions defining the trade-off will depend on the variety used, the management level, the initial inoculum level, and the flood pattern. The future development of ufra control strategies by postponing the time of sowing or transplanting must consider the conditions under which an interior solution is generated. The model does not take into account additional benefits realized only in successive years as the initial level of inoculum is progressively reduced. ■

Ripcord — a synthetic pyrethroid against rice tungro virus

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The possibility of controlling or minimizing incidence of tungro virus was tried by controlling the vector insect through the

Data on rice tungro virus incidence. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment ^a	Rice tungro (%)		Stunted unproductive population (%)
	60th DT	75th DT	
1. RS with FMC 35001 at 0.04% + 1% urea + RZP of carbofuran at 0.25 kg a.i./ha on 20th DT	77	82	68
2. Treatment 1 + FS with FMC 35001 at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 45th DT	79	82	74
3. Treatment 1 + FS with FMC 35001 at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 25 th and 45 th DT	75	79	68
4. RS with Ripcord at 0.01% + 1% urea + RZP of carbofuran at 0.25 kg ai/ha on 20th DT	79	81	72
5. Treatment 4 + FS with Ripcord at 50 g ai/ha on 45 th DT	77	85	65
6. RS with Ripcord at 0.01% + 1% urea + FS with Ripcord at 50 g ai/ha on 25th and 45th DT	28	52	15
7. RS with carbofuran SP at 0.04% + 1% urea + RZP of carbofuran at 0.25 ai/ha on 20th DT	77	84	66
8. Treatment 7 + FS with carbofuran SP at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 45 th DT	72	84	66
9. RS with carbofuran SP at 0.04% + 1% urea + FS with carbofuran 50 SP at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 25th and 45 th DT	52	70	38
10. RS with chlorpyrifos at 0.04% + 1% urea + RZP of carbofuran at 0.25 kg ai/ha on 20th DT	80	91	68
11. Treatment 10 + FS with chlorpyrifos at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 45th DT	75	84	64
12. RS with chlorpyrifos at 0.04% + 1% urea + FS with chlorpyrifos at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 25th and 45th DT	76	82	64
13. Control	96	98	81
CD (P-0.05%)	6.8	8.9	5.4

^aRS = root soaking, RZP = root-zone placement, FS = foliar spray, DT = day(s) after transplanting.

following insecticides: carbofuran 3% G, carbofuran 50% SP, FMC 35001 (carbo-sulphan) 24% EC, Ripcord (cypermethrin-synthetic pyrethroid) 5% EC, and Dursban (chlorpyrifos) 20% EC. Three methods of application were tried: root soaking, root-zone placement, and foliar spray. Tungro incidence was assessed on tungro-susceptible variety ADT31 60 and 75 days after transplanting (DT). At

harvest the nonproductive population stunted by tungro was also assessed.

Root soaking with Ripcord along with 1% urea followed by foliar spray with Ripcord on the 25th and 45th DT gave low tungro incidence (see table). The synthetic pyrethroid Ripcord can be effective in reducing tungro incidence if used as foliar spray from 10 to 15 DT 3 times at 10- to 15-day intervals. ■

Chemical control of Helminthosporiose of rice

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Helminthosporiose of rice, caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae*, is widespread in Kerala; its incidence is severe during the rabi (Oct–Jan) cropping season.

A field experiment on chemical control of the disease was conducted at the Pattambi RRS in the 1977–78 kharif and

rabi seasons. Seven fungicides — edifenphos EC, zineb, mancozeb, captafol, copper oxychloride, Aureofungin sol, and IBP — were sprayed on plants of the susceptible variety Benibhog three times at 14-day intervals beginning at 30 days after transplanting. The disease incidence was recorded 10 days after the final spraying and graded using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Plants treated with zineb had the lowest disease index in both seasons and a corresponding increase in grain yield.